

Site: _____ Season NIS 80

Area: EST Square ^{N11}F9-10 Locus Number (16) PACKED SAND

Progress of Excavation 1.20 (23/VI/80) Begin moving (16) Shows

Mod Brick, some stones packed in packed sand matrix
Work w/ fas. under dirty sand packed (16), shows
clean fine sand - should be level (2) // 24/VI/80: (16)
clearing continues, N half of square finished by end of day, Roman(?)
pottery comes up (ribbed amphora neck handle) This probably disturbed
- out of context

Locus Description Packed sand w/ some stone

Location in Square Across Square

Under Locus (19) LOOSE SAND Over Locus (2) FINE CLEAN SAND

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels NF: 9.98 SE: 9.52 SW: 8.83 NW: 9.03 CENTER 9.41

Analysis of non-artifactual materials SOME FRAGS MOD. BRICK; LIMESTONE

$$\begin{array}{r} 1.62 \\ 2.78 \\ \hline 11.40 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 11.46 \\ 1.99 \\ \hline 9.41 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 11.210 \\ 1.92 \\ \hline 9.98 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 11.410 \\ 1.88 \\ \hline 9.52 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 11.410 \\ 2.57 \\ \hline 8.83 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{r} 11.410 \\ 2.37 \\ \hline 9.03 \end{array}$$